

EcoPlastic

Eco conversion of lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers.

D6.8 THIRD ANNUAL REPORT ON DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

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Abbreviation list

(A-Z)

AVE – Avecom, Belgium

DEC – Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

DECP – Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Plan

EC – European Commission

EIC – European Innovation Council

IMGGE – Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, Serbia

KER – Key Exploitable Result

KPI – Key Performance Indicator

KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan, *i.e.*, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

NL - Newsletter

NOVA – Associação para a Inovação e Desenvolvimento da FCT, *i.e.*, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal

TUS – Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest, Ireland

Y1 – First year of the EcoPlastiC project

Y2 – Second year of the EcoPlastiC project

Y3 – Third year of the EcoPlastiC project

1. Executive summary

This deliverable **D6.8** provides a detailed report on the progress towards the implementation of the dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy, designed and defined in the first year of the EcoPlastiC project. General framework for implementation of these activities was previously described in the deliverable **D6.1** Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan (M6) and was updated in the deliverables **D6.3** First annual report on dissemination, exploitation and communication activities (M12) and **D6.7** Second annual report on dissemination, exploitation and communication activities (M24).

The report **D6.8** gives overview of the key dissemination and communication activities during the third year of the EcoPlastiC project (1 October 2024 – 30 September 2025) and focuses on the main key performance indicators defined in the DEC plan. It summaries the main activities of all partners, including presence at industry events, conferences and symposia, project advertisement in the media, published results from the project, visits to higher education institutions and schools and project promotion to the public, as well as a successful EcoPlastiC newsletter campaigns. Each activity has been put against initial targets and indicators in the Table 13 in Chapter 4 to measure success of the actions taken during the final year of the project. Our exploitation progress has been updated by all EcoPlastiC partners and is presented in the **Annex I** (Tables 15-18).

Commercialisation Feasibility (CFF) study was done by TUS, engaging with 21 companies as given in **Annex II**. The aim was to gather industry perspectives on the potential of CicloPak and CicloSeal in replacing conventional plastic-based materials with bio-based, compostable and recyclable alternatives, focusing on key performance requirements. Many expressed willingness to support testing, provide samples, share technical data, and in some cases offer letters of support for funding, underlining both strong market interest and the need for further validation. In addition, EIC INNOVATION RADAR at the end of project is presented in the **Annex III**.

In the third year (Y3) of the EcoPlastiC project, which surpassed the successes of the Y1 and Y2, we significantly advanced our efforts to engage stakeholders and expand the project's reach to a broader audience. Building on the foundation established in the previous years, we not only strengthened awareness of the project's objectives and activities, but also enhanced the visibility for our project team and partners. Numerous DEC activities were performed jointly and in synergies with other EC supported projects. As a result, all activities and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the original DEC Plan have been successfully met.

2. Introduction

EcoPlastiC started in October 2022 as a 3-year Horizon Europe Pathfinder programme project funded by the EC and EIC. Its Consortium involves five partners from four EU countries (TUS from Ireland, AVE from Belgium, NOVA from Portugal and KTH from Sweden) and one associated country (IMGGE from Serbia). Four partners (TUS, NOVA, IMGGE, KTH) are research institutions, and one partner (AVE) is a Small to Medium Sized Enterprise (SME).

EcoPlastiC set out to offer an efficient solution to the widespread issue of PET plastic pollution by transforming it into eco-friendly plastic prototypes, specifically high-performance bioplastics. The project focuses on converting lower-grade PET and mixed, resistant PET plastic waste into advanced biopolymers, directing this waste into eco-products that can be continuously recycled in a bio-loop. These innovative eco-plastics and products are designed as drop-in alternatives, enabling smooth integration into industrial processes and easy adoption by consumers.

The DEC Plan (**D6.1**) in M6 described in detail the approach and planning for communication and dissemination of the EcoPlastiC project and its results. The Y1 report (**D6.3**) in M12 provided an update on the DEC Plan, summarising the initial activities undertaken by the partners to fulfil the project's objectives. The Y2 report (**D6.7**) in M24 focused on bringing the project even closer to all stakeholders, expanding participation in scientific and industry events, and strengthening collaboration and knowledge exchange with other EU-funded projects.

In this final reporting year, our efforts have been directed towards maximising the project's visibility, ensuring wide dissemination of results, and solidifying connections with stakeholders across academia, industry and the public. The steady growth in outreach indicators over the three years reflects the effectiveness of these activities and confirms that EcoPlastiC has successfully delivered on its communication and dissemination objectives.

3. Communication strategy

We previously reported the development of the visual identity materials, such as EcoPlastiC logo, the watermark for official documents (such as minutes, conference reports *etc.*) and the Power Point presentation template. We also reported on the printed materials that were developed within the Y1 (EcoPlastiC brochure and 3 versions of the roll up) and Y2 (bookmark, notepad, folder, ballpoint pens) of the project.

No new promotional material was developed in Y3 and the existing materials are available for download at the EcoPlastiC website: <https://ecoplasticproject.eu/download>

3.1. Communication and dissemination channels

For appropriate communication and dissemination to all target groups, EcoPlastiC team uses different channels providing information through a variety of formats. The summary and comparison between activities in Y2 (**Table 1**) and Y3 (**Table 2**) is shown.

Table 1. Indicators and targets for the website and social media on 27/09/2024 (**Y2**).

Activity Y2	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Website	2059 unique visitors	Visits per year: <500 poor 500-1000 good >1000 excellent	42 news
X/Twitter	356 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	119 posts + 14 reposts
LinkedIn	362 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	123 posts + 4 reposts
Facebook	38 followers + 19 likes	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	119 posts + 6 reposts
Instagram	280 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	80 posts
Newsletter	218 subscribers	4 campaigns	2 campaign

Table 2. Indicators and targets for the website and social media on 25/09/2025 (**Y3**).

Activity Y3	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Website	1834 unique visitors	Visits per year: <500 poor 500-1000 good >1000 excellent	79 news
X/Twitter	228 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	209 posts + 17 reposts

LinkedIn	562 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	213 posts + 12 reposts
Facebook	51 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	209 posts + 6 reposts
Instagram	354 followers	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	155 posts
Newsletter	213 subscribers	4 campaigns	4 campaign

More details on the website analytics (3.1.1), the social media accounts (3.1.2) and the newsletter (3.1.3) are provided below.

3.1.1. EcoPlastiC Y3 website analytics

The primary source of information about the project is the EcoPlastiC website, created and administrated by IMGGE (www.ecoplasticproject.eu) and it is one of the most relevant dissemination tools for reaching the largest audience possible, including the scientific community, the project's stakeholders, relevant industries, but also the wider public.

We use the [Plausible](#) to study web analytics, and the report for the past 12 months (from 01/10/2024 - 25/09/2025) is shown below (also available at this [link](#)):

All 5 partner countries (1st place Serbia, 2nd place Ireland, 4th place Portugal, 7th place Belgium, 8th place Sweden) are in the Top 10 countries that visited the website (on Thursday, 25/09/2025):

Country	Visitors ↓	%
Serbia	1.8k	32.2%
Ireland	456	8.1%
United States	436	7.8%
Portugal	263	4.7%
Netherlands	223	4%
Germany	204	3.6%
Belgium	188	3.3%
Sweden	173	3.1%
France	162	2.9%
India	150	2.7%

All EcoPlastiC social media pages (3rd place LinkedIn, 6th place Facebook, 8th place Instagram, 10th place X) are in the Top 10 sources (on Thursday, 25/09/2025):

Source	Visitors ↓	Bounce Rate	Visit Duration
Direct / None	2.5k	58%	2m 52s
Google	1.6k	59%	1m 23s
LinkedIn	369	73%	1m 06s
imgge.bg.ac.rs	201	65%	1m 40s
Bing	133	45%	1m 48s
Facebook	115	75%	22s
Gmail	83	66%	1m 21s
Instagram	56	67%	53s
newsletter	56	68%	53s
Twitter	46	64%	1m 04s

3.1.2. Social media accounts

The EcoPlastiC project maintained an active presence on X, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram throughout its three years, with Y3 marking the culmination of our social media strategy. Building on the strong foundations laid in Y1 and Y2, our final-year efforts focused on consolidating and maximising audience engagement. We shared timely updates on project meetings, milestones and participation in key events and conferences.

In this closing stage, we placed greater emphasis on connecting the project to the broader conversation on the circular economy and sustainability. By positioning EcoPlastiC within a network of related initiatives and projects, we crafted a cohesive and compelling narrative that highlighted our contributions and impact. This integrated approach not only sustained follower interest, but also reinforced the project’s visibility and relevance as it reached its conclusion.

<p>X (formerly Twitter): @_EcoPlastiC_ https://twitter.com/EcoPlastiC</p>	
<p>Facebook page: Ecoplastic https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100088412644481</p>	

3.1.3. Newsletters

As stated in the DEC plan, “During the lifetime of the project, four electronic newsletters (NLs) will be prepared and distributed to the project target groups, project partners, networks and posted on website”.

We previously reported that NL#1 [LINK](#) was released in M10 (July 2023, Y1) to an audience of 191 subscribers. The NL#2 [LINK](#) was released in M19 (April 2024, Y2) to an audience of 213 subscribers.

In Y3, the NL#3 [LINK](#) was released in M27 (December 2024) to an audience of 221 subscribers and NL#4 [LINK](#) was released in M36 (September 2025) to an audience of 213 subscribers.

Each Newsletter contains the following sections: Introduction & Welcome, EcoPlastiC partners, EcoPlastiC research highlights, EcoPlastiC@events, EcoPlastiC in the media, EcoPlastiC publications and the Contact section, reflecting main activities and impacts of the project. All NLs are available on the Downloads page of the EcoPlastiC website.

3.2. Activities in Y3

The summary of EcoPlastiC activities and their comparison between Y2 (**Table 3**) and Y3 (**Table 4**) are shown, with indicators and targets clearly explained.

Table 3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets for the EcoPlastiC activities in Y2 on 27/09/2024.

Activity Y2	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <5 poor 5-7 good >7 excellent	15 events attended
Conferences	Number of conferences, symposia, and workshops attendances	Attendances: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	16 conferences attended
Scientific publications	Number of articles published	Published articles: <5 poor 5-10 good >10 excellent	6 publications
Media releases	Number of media	Media: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	8 media releases

Education and public engagement at partners' institutes	Number of engagements	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	3 lectures/visits
School visits	Number of visits	Visits: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	16 visits
Women in Science events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	1
Special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives	Number of events engagement	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	3 participations

Table 4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets for the EcoPlastiC activities in Y3 on 25/09/2025.

Activity Y3	Indicator (Audience)	Target number	Numbers (Activity)
Events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <5 poor 5-7 good >7 excellent	16 events attended
Conferences	Number of conferences, symposia, and workshops attendances	Attendances: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	24 conferences attended
Scientific publications	Number of articles published	Published articles: <5 poor 5-10 good >10 excellent	8 publications
Media releases	Number of media	Media: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	4 media releases

Education and public engagement at partners' institutes	Number of engagements	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	6 lectures/visits
School visits	Number of visits	Visits: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	17 visits
Women in Science events	Number of events attendances	Attendances: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	6 events
Special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives	Number of events engagement	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	4 participations

More details on the attended events (3.2.1), conferences (3.2.2), scientific publications (3.2.3), media releases (3.2.4), education and public engagement (3.2.5), school visits (3.2.6), women in science events (3.2.7) and special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives (3.2.8) are provided below.

3.2.1. Events

During Y3, the project partners represented EcoPlastiC at 16 events across Europe and their list is presented in **Table 5**, while a photo from the event (where applicable) together with a short description is also provided below **Table 5**.

Table 5. List of events from Y3 where the EcoPlastiC project was presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	The Aquarama Trade Fair for water technology	AVE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	17/10/2024	Leuven, Belgium	1300
2	Seminar at IMGGE	IMGGE	Presenter	Highlights of EcoPlastiC	22/10/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	48
3	Festival of the Future	AVE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	26/11/2024	Merelbeke, Belgium	400
4	REsponsible BuSiness DialoGue (ESG)	IMGGE	Exhibitors	EcoPlastiC project	02/12/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	95

5	Pitch Perfect and Boost the European Bioeconomy 2024	AVE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	02-03/12/2024	Brussels, Belgium	446
6	European Workshop on Biotechnology	IMGGE	Participant	Biobased Materials	20-23/01/2025	Sion, Switzerland	25
7	3rd Regional Meeting "PACKAGING AND PACKAGING WASTE"	IMGGE	Presenter	Innovative use of mixed packaging waste: Production of PHA and BNC as sustainable solutions for food and pharmaceutical packaging	25/02/2025	Novi Sad, Serbia	50
8	Scientific Research Projects Tailored to Industry - Experiences and Opportunities in the Pharmaceutical Industry	IMGGE	Presenter	Bacterial nanocellulose - towards greener cosmetics and nutraceuticals	12/03/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	106
9	Restoring the Natural Balance	AVE	Presenter	Celebrating 30 years of Avecom	08/04/2025	Ghent, Belgium	120
10	Microplastics for Breakfast	IMGGE	Presenter	Eco-Biotechnology and Drug Development group at IMGGE	10/04/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	>100
11	TUS Engineering Expo 2025	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	10/04/2025	Athlone, Ireland	>200
12	Expo FCT NOVA Open Day	NOVA	Exhibitors	Biopolymers	02/05/2025	Lisbon, Portugal	5100 students, 450 profs from 65 schools
13	PHA Symposium Session #2: Blends & Composites	TUS	Speaker	Biocomposites for packaging applications	16/05/2025	online	38
14	My First Horizon	IMGGE	Speaker	EcoPlastiC project	21/05/2025	Belgrade, serbia	80
15	67th International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements	IMGGE	Exhibitor	EcoPlastiC project	20-23/05/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	17548
16	World Environment Day "Plastic and health – Invisible waste, visible consequences"	IMGGE	Panelist	EcoPlastiC project	05/06/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	62

1. The Aquarama Trade Fair for water technology

Avecom was an exhibitor at the Aquarama trade fair & conference. A prominent expo and conference focusing on water technology and treatment, this event was a key gathering for industry professionals and water sector enthusiasts. Flyers on the EcoPlastiC project were distributed.

2. Seminar at IMGGE

EcoPlastiC project was presented at the internal weekly seminar of the Institute of Molecular Genetics and genetic Engineering (Serbia).

3. Festival of the Future

The Festival of the Future features inspiring keynote, as well as an interactive Experience Market showcasing cutting-edge innovations from universities, businesses, and entrepreneurs. Attendees can explore advances in sustainability, technology, and societal solutions.

4. REsponsible BuSiness DialoGue (ESG)

Within the ESG Conference organised by the AmCham Serbia, at the 'Sustainability Solutions Fair', research institutes and companies had the opportunity to present their innovative solutions. This segment offered a platform for showcasing projects that focus on sustainability, such as EcoPlastiC, providing a valuable chance for companies to connect and explore potential collaborations.

5. Pitch Perfect and Boost the European Bioeconomy 2024

"Pitch Perfect and Boost the European Bioeconomy" aims at giving early-stage startups the chance to pitch their ideas to investors. The pitches are divided into categories such as microbial protein transition players, artificial intelligence in biomanufacturing, microbes and gaseous feedstocks, scaling up novel biomaterials and processes, leading pilot facilities for the bioeconomy, and emerging innovative technologies for the bioeconomy. The event is designed to drive innovation and investment in the European bioeconomy.

6. European Workshop on Biotechnology

This workshop was organised by European Federation of Biotechnology (Division Biobased Materials), University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland and The School of Engineering and Architecture of Fribourg. This workshop was organized with the idea to provide the attendees with the basic knowledge about biopolymers: how are they produced, processed and what are the opportunities for their application. There were 13 attendees from different countries (2 from Austria, 1 from Spain, 4 from Italy, 2 from Serbia, 3 from Switzerland and 1 from Israel).

7. 3rd Regional Meeting "PACKAGING AND PACKAGING WASTE"

The event focused on the implementation of new international standards for circular economy practices in Serbia, particularly in the areas of packaging and recycling. Experts discussed topics such as EU directives, plastic recycling, and the use of biomaterials in circular economy processes. Other discussions covered food packaging regulations, the impact of harmful chemicals like PFAS, and the challenges and goals of recycling, including upcycling waste into new packaging materials.

8. Scientific Research Projects Tailored to Industry - Experiences and Opportunities in the Pharmaceutical Industry

Completed and ongoing projects in the pharmaceutical sector were presented, with the aim of encouraging cooperation between companies and public scientific research organisations. These projects aim to develop innovative products and services with high market potential. Members from IMGGE presented the EcoPlastiC project and the collaboration with the company Esensa, as well as possibilities for future cooperation with the industry.

9. Restoring the Natural Balance

During this conference for clients and suppliers, Avecom presented also the EcoPlastiC project during the celebration of 30 years of Avecom.

10. Microplastics for Breakfast

At the first meeting of micro- and nano-plastics researchers from Serbia, Montenegro & Bosnia and Herzegovina "Microplastics for Breakfast", more than 100 researchers and their teams presented their latest projects discoveries. Experts continuously demonstrate and establish the importance of a topic that, until recently, was not widely discussed, which stems from the global plastic pollution.

11. TUS Engineering Expo 2025

The TUS Engineering Expo 2025 took place at the Midlands Campus in Athlone (Ireland), showcasing the innovative spirit and technical expertise of the Faculty of Engineering and Informatics at the Technological University of the Shannon. This dynamic event featured over 170 undergraduate projects and 30 PhD research initiatives, highlighting cutting-edge applied research across diverse disciplines. Designed as a collaborative platform, the expo brought together students and researchers to exchange ideas, foster interdisciplinary partnerships and inspire the development of future innovations. Over 300 staff members and students who attended the event had the opportunity to explore groundbreaking projects that address real-world challenges and push the boundaries of engineering and informatics.

12. Expo FCT NOVA Open Day

The partners from NOVA participated and shared their research with hundreds of curious students, teachers, and families. Through hands-on experiments and interactive demos, visitors got a taste of the science behind their work in biopolymers, sustainable bioprocesses and environmental biotechnology.

13. PHA Symposium Session #2: Blends & Composites

This online session focused on how blending and compounding PHA with other materials can enhance performance, expand application possibilities and tailor material properties for industrial use. Topics that were covered were formulation and blending strategies, composite development and design, processing techniques and scale-up and real-world applications and case studies.

14. My First Horizon

At the training event “My First Horizon” an insightful and interactive talk was delivered by IMGGE Team Leader during the panel ‘Making partnerships and the project consortium’. She spoke about the project and Pathfinder experiences, underscoring the purpose of this event to encourage, motivate and strengthen the Serbian scientific community in applying for Horizon Europe calls.

15. 67th International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements

At the training event “My First Horizon” an insightful and interactive talk was delivered by IMGGE Team Leader during the panel ‘Making partnerships and the project consortium’. She spoke about the project and Pathfinder experiences, underscoring the purpose of this event to encourage, motivate and strengthen the Serbian scientific community in applying for Horizon Europe calls.

16. World Environment Day “Plastic and health – Invisible waste, visible consequences”

Topics discussed included the ways which researchers are developing to repurpose plastic waste from 3D printing, transforming it into functional biomaterials to reduce environmental impact. The panel also brushed on whether biomaterials can limit the intake of micro and nano plastics, providing a safer alternative to conventional plastics. The IMGGE communicated that they are actively working on projects that address microplastic pollution through innovative technologies and projects like EcoPlastiC. These efforts aim to enhance waste management, improve health protection and create sustainable solutions for future applications.

3.2.2. Conferences

During Y3, the results from the EcoPlastiC project were presented in 17 scientific conferences through 24 scientific contributions, including plenary lectures, invited lectures and poster and oral presentations. The list of conferences is presented in **Table 6**, while a photo from the event (where applicable) together with a short description is provided below **Table 6**.

Table 6. List of scientific conferences in Y3 where the EcoPlastiC project results were presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	VII Congress of the Serbian Genetic Society	IMGGE	Invited Speaker	Environmental microorganisms and their populations as biotechnological solution to plastic pollution	02-05/10/2024	Zlatibor, Serbia	255
2		IMGGE	Presenter (poster)	Laboratory evolved microbial consortium towards arabinoxylan can degrade polyurethane			

3	3 rd Serbian Conference on Materials Application and Technology	IMGGE	Invited Speaker	Nanocellulose: From bacteria to breakthrough materials	16-18/10/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	90
4	International Symposium on Biopolymers (ISBP2024)	IMGGE	Keynote Speaker	Tuning properties of microbial biopolymers towards biomedical applications	20-23/10/2024	Penang Island, Malaysia	380
5		NOVA	Keynote Speaker	Breaking the plastic wave: Innovating with biopolymer production			
6		IMGGE	Presenter (poster presentation)	Development and characterization of novel biobased polyurethane films reinforced with bacterial biomass			
7		IMGGE	Presenter (poster presentation)	PHB and PHB-PHO composites with immobilized <i>Streptomyces</i> DG19 spores for enhanced polymer degradation			
8	14th European Symposium on Biochemical Engineering Sciences (ESBES)	NOVA	Presenter (oral presentation)	Upcycling of PET-based plastic waste into biodegradable polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) using mixed microbial cultures	21-23/10/2024	Copenhagen, Denmark	315
9	2nd European Society of Applied Biocatalysis (ESAB) Congress	IMGGE	Presenter (poster presentation)	Greener extraction of intracellular poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) from <i>Zobellella denitrificans</i> biomass using enzyme cocktails and deep eutectic solvents	25-27/11/2024	online	61
10	Winter School on Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) and Disinfection By-Products (DBPs): Occurrence, Impact and Elimination	NOVA	Invited Speaker	Biological Removal and Recovery of Micro/plastics	25-26/11/2024	Vila Nova de Gaia, Portugal	250

11	TUS Research Week	TUS	Presenter (poster presentation on 18-02-2025) and panel speaker (Circular Systems and Nature panel)	Sustainable alternatives to PP: Advancing Circular Economy with PET and PBT in contact lens molding	17-21/02/2025	Limerick, Ireland	80
12		TUS	Presenter (oral presentation on 19-02-2025) and panel speaker (Sustainability and Creativity in Research panel)	Leveraging life cycle assessment for sustainable plastic solutions: A case study of the EcoPlastiC project			60
13		TUS	Presenter (poster presentation on 20-02-2025)	Near-infrared-induced high-performance antimicrobial active coating for medical textiles based in easy-to-synthesize natural catechin with full end of life circularity			50
14	1 st International Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Toward Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US)	NOVA	Plenary Lecturer	Unlocking the Potential of Waste for Sustainable Biopolymer Manufacturing	05-07/05/25	Basel Switzerland	150
15	21st International Conference on Renewable Resources and Biorefineries (RRB)	NOVA	Presenter (oral presentation)	PET as bacterial carbon source - a new hope for plastic pollution	02-04/06/2025	Turku, Finland	246
16	19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment (ICCE)	IMGGE	Presenter (poster presentation)	Bio-Upcycling of PET Plastic Waste into Bacterial Nanocellulose Reinforced by Poly(vinyl alcohol) as a Platinum Nanoparticles Support Efficient in Methanol Oxidation	08-12/06/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	>450

17	BioBased Future 2025: Green Bioprocessing for Innovative Bioactive Products	IMGGE	Presenter (poster presentation)	From plastic waste to nutraceutical-conversion of PET containing hydrolysates to bacterial nanocellulose with pomegranate extract	16-18/06/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	96
18	NOVA FCT Science Days	NOVA	Presenter (poster presentation)	Biotechnology for Circularity: Sustainable Solutions from Waste	17-18/06/2025	Lisbon, Portugal	50
19		NOVA	Presenter (poster presentation)	Microbial products: the solution for a sustainable future			
20	EPF European Polymer Congress	IMGGE	Presenter (oral presentation)	Merging polyurethanes and polyhydroxyalkanoates into high-performance polymers	22-27/06/2025	Groningen, Netherlands	>1200
21	8th Workshop on PPB in wastewater treatment: challenges, opportunities and potential for resource recovery.	NOVA	Presenter (invited lecture)	Emerging strategies for the bioconversion of wastes into biodegradable polymers	01-02/07/2025	Ankara, Turkey	35
22	FEMS MICRO Milan 2025 Congress and Exhibition	NOVA	Presenter (poster presentation)	Harnessing the power of bacteria to fight recalcitrant post-consumer PET-waste burden	14-17/07/2025	Milan, Italy	>2000
23	The Eleventh International Symposium on Engineering Plastics	KTH	Keynote speaker	Protein plastics - sources, properties and applications	03-06/08/2025	Harbin, China	250
24	International Conference of MIKROBIOKOSMOS & Central and Eastern Europe Symposium on Microbial Ecology (CEESME)	IMGGE	Presenter (poster presentation)	Tuning properties by blending bacterial polymers polyhydroxyalkanoates and nanocellulose	22-24/09/2025	Thessaloniki, Greece	>400

1-2. VII Congress of the Serbian Genetic Society

This was an international conference covering a wide range of topics: (1) Population genetics and genomics, (2) Evolutionary and conservation genetics, (3) Microbial genetics, (4) Medical genetics, (5) Challenges of genotoxicology in the 21st century, (6) New breeding technologies and perspectives, (7) Bioinformatics and big data analysis. It gathered over 250 participants and included 12 plenary lectures, 33 invited lectures, 44 short oral presentations, 128 posters, 13 sponsor presentations and it also had a workshop, a mini-symposium and 2 round tables.

3. 3rd Serbian Conference on Materials Application and Technology

The 3rd Serbian Conference on Materials Application and Technology (SCOM) is the new home for all technology-related materials applications research, with a special emphasis on advanced materials design, manufacturing and integration, as well as novel materials-based technologies, including energy, healthcare, electronics, optics, microfluidics, sensors, food safety, etc. The aim of this conference was to bridge the gap between fundamental research and industry in Serbia.

4-7. International Symposium on Biopolymers (ISBP2024)

The 19th International Symposium on Biopolymers – “Towards Safe and Sustainable Biopolymers for our Future” included 4 plenary lectures, 16 keynote lectures, 19 invited lectures, 46 oral presentations and 85 poster presentations. Topic were Engineering advances in biopolymer synthesis, Biosynthesis and characterisation of novel biopolymers, Exploring building blocks for bio-based polymers, Biodegradation pathways, Environmental impacts of biopolymers, Sustainable feedstocks for biopolymer production, Challenges in the industrial production of biopolymers, PHA waste management, Exploration of other biopolymers and bio-based polymers, Applications of novel biopolymers in various industries, Rubber biosynthesis and biodegradation.

8. 14th European Symposium on Biochemical Engineering Sciences (ESBES)

The 14th European Symposium on Biochemical Engineering Sciences, which had 245 registered participants, was organized jointly with the Fermentation Based Manufacturing Symposium, adding 70 extra participants. The central topic was “Biochemical engineering for the sustainable processes of the future”. Research topics covered were biocatalysis, biotechnology and metabolic engineering, novel upstream and downstream process concepts, bioenergy, (bio)pharmaceutical processing, bioprocesses for food engineering, precision fermentation, circular (Bio)Economy and processing, digitalization, advances in fluid and solids process engineering, Industrial water and wastewater technology, new (bio)materials for process engineering, and education.

9. 2nd European Society of Applied Biocatalysis (ESAB) Congress

ESAB has been founded in 1980 and has the mission of promoting the development of Applied Biocatalysis throughout Europe. The aims of ESAB are to promote initiatives in areas of growing scientific and industrial interest of importance within the field of Applied Biocatalysis.

10. Winter School on Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) and Disinfection By-Products (DBPs): Occurrence, Impact and Elimination

The objective of this event was to share the latest advances in the occurrence, impact and elimination of contaminants and to present new solutions for providing alternative water sources for crop production and safe drinking water.

11-13. TUS Research Week

At Coonagh Campus in Limerick, the participants engaged in in-depth discussions on sustainable design, resource efficiency and nature-based solutions. Drawing from their project experiences, they exchanged insights on circular systems and explored various impact scenarios, contributing to a deeper understanding of sustainable innovation and its real-world applications.

The presentation of Eduardo Lanzagorta-Garcia aimed to provide a general overview of the process required to produce a Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), using the LCA for the EcoPlastic project as an example to showcase the advantages of applying this methodology to identify areas of improvement regarding sustainability. The participant was also part of the panel titled “Sustainability and Creativity in Research”, answering questions related to the overlap and differences between engineering and design, in the context of sustainable products.

The poster of Zeliha Ece Ozcelik showcased sustainable, natural-based solutions with full end-of-life circularity, emphasizing innovative approaches to medical textile coatings. In addition to the poster presentation, TUS team engaged in insightful discussions with fellow researchers, exchanging ideas on sustainability and material science. The event provided a valuable platform to highlight cutting-edge research and foster future collaborations.

14. 1st International Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Toward Zero Waste (FULLRECO4US)

The objective of this event was to discuss the latest approaches to waste recycling and valorization and to promote interdisciplinary networks. The conference included relevant topics such as Biopolymer & bioplastic production, Innovative processes, Eco-efficient solutions for waste management, Circular economy, Life cycle assessments, Zero waste approach Sustainable waste management and Social-economy issues & policies.

15. 21st International Conference on Renewable Resources and Biorefineries (RRB)

The theme for this year was “Moving Beyond Carbon Neutral” and the presentation topics covered Algal biorefinery, biobased chemicals and biodegradable materials, biocatalysis and novel fermentation processes, bioenergy and thermochemical transformation, biorefining, carbon capture & utilization, catalysis for renewables and kinetics, downstream processing, marine bio-economy, polysaccharides, pretreatment and transformation of lignocellulosics, sustainability and circular economy, synthetic biology and biofoundries, valorisation of food residues and wood chemistry and engineering.

16. 19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment (ICCE)

Continual knowledge development is essential to ensure a healthy environment and the safe progress of society. ICCE 2025 aims to accelerate this process by addressing a wide range of challenges and developments from the perspective of Environmental Chemistry, serving societal sustainability goals.

17. BioBased Future 2025: Green Bioprocessing for Innovative Bioactive Products

The conference brought together researchers, industry professionals and stakeholders to explore the forefront of sustainable bioprocessing and its applications in creating high-value bioactive products. This event aimed to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange, driving innovation in the development of bio-based solutions that align with a sustainable future. With a focus on leveraging renewable resources, enhancing process efficiency and developing valuable bioactive products, the conference emphasizes the integration of scientific research and industrial applications for a circular economy.

18-19. NOVA FCT Science Days

The objective of this event was to showcase the research developed at NOVA FCT, creating the opportunity to establish new collaborations between colleagues working at this institution.

20. EPF European Polymer Congress

As the most significant European congress in the field of Polymer Science and Technology, it has evolved into a biennial convergence of considerable scale, attracting an ever-growing and diverse participation. Under the theme "Polymers for a Sustainable Future", it brought together scientists engaged in macromolecular chemistry, polymer science, physics of polymers and polymer materials, modern polymer applications, polymer reaction engineering, rheology and polymer processing, polymer characterization methods and more.

21. 8th Workshop on PPB in wastewater treatment: challenges, opportunities and potential for resource recovery

The objective of this event was to foster the dialogue between industry and academia on purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) in environmental biotechnology, with special emphasis on wastewater treatment and resource recovery.

22. FEMS MICRO Milan 2025 Congress and Exhibition

Fuelled by innovation, expertise, and community, FEMS MICRO 2025 brought together more than 2,000 attendees from over 95 countries for four dynamic days of collaboration and exchange. Centred on the theme Magnifying microbial impact, the FEMS MICRO Milan Congress & Exhibition went beyond traditional research showcases, exploring how microbiology is driving practical solutions to global challenges. Through keynotes, workshops, and interactive sessions, the event presented cutting-edge research, sparked meaningful connections, and reflected the strength and diversity of our field.

23. The Eleventh International Symposium on Engineering Plastics

International Symposium on Engineering Plastics (EP) is a biennial academic conference organized by Institute of Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, aiming to provide a high-profile platform for world-wide polymer scientists to exchange up-to-date research progresses and share innovative ideas on the future development of polymer materials. The EP2025 continue dthe commitment to advancing polymer materials science and technology by setting its slogan as “Polymer Materials for a Better Life”.

24. International Conference of MIKROBIOKOSMOS

The MBK-CEESME 2025 conference brought together leading minds in microbial ecology, biotechnology and environmental microbiology. This year, the event served as a hub for knowledge exchange, networking and pointing the cutting-edge research across terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, as well as a scientific fest on all possible (and impossible!) aspects of microbial life in terrestrial and aquatic habitats, agriculture and food science, biotechnology and bioengineering, climate change, bio-economy, antimicrobial resistance and host-microbe interactions.

3.2.3. Scientific publications

During Y3, EcoPlastiC has produced and published 8 scientific publications in international refereed journal that are listed in **Table 7**. They are deposited in the open repository Zenodo and are uploaded and accessible on the project website. The [EcoPlastiC community](#) was also created, where all public deliverables are available, and all scientific publications that acknowledged the EcoPlastiC project can be found [here](#).

Additional two publications co-authored by KTH and TUS have recently been accepted, and four manuscripts are in preparation, as described in the Technical Report.

Table 7. List of scientific publications in Y3

#	Year	Title + Link	Journal	IF	Partner	Citation	Zenodo
1	2024	Near-Infrared-Induced High-Performance Antimicrobial Active Coating for Medical Textiles Based on Easy-to-Synthesize Natural Catechin with Full End of Life Circularity	ACS Sustainable Chemistry and Engineering	7.1	TUS	Zeliha Ece Ozcelik, Buket Alkan Tas, Necdet Ozcelik, Bor Shin Chee, Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia, Marija Mojicevic, Margaret Brennan Fournet, Cuneyt Erdinc Tas, Near-Infrared-Induced High-Performance Antimicrobial Active Coating for Medical Textiles Based on Easy-to-Synthesize Natural Catechin with Full End of Life Circularity, ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng. 2024, 12, 49, 17936–17951. https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.4c08280	https://zenodo.org/records/14444031
2	2024	Development of Antimicrobial Blends of Bacteria Nanocellulose Derived from Plastic Waste and Polyhydroxybutyrate Enhanced with Essential Oils	Polymers	4.7	TUS	Da Silva Pereira, E. H., Nicevic, M., Garcia, E. L., Moritz, V. F., Ozcelik, Z. E., Tas, B. A., & Fournet, M. B. (2024). Development of Antimicrobial Blends of Bacteria Nanocellulose Derived from Plastic Waste and Polyhydroxybutyrate Enhanced with Essential Oils. Polymers, 16(24), 3490. https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16243490	https://zenodo.org/records/14551417
3	2025	Bacterial nanocellulose and its oxidized form as functional carriers for pomegranate peel extract: A sustainable approach to bioactive delivery	Future Foods	7.2	IMGGE	Vuk Filipovic, Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic, Katarina Savikin, Jelena Zivkovic, Jelena Mudric, Nemanja Krgovic, Marijana Ponjavic, Bacterial nanocellulose and its oxidized form as functional carriers for pomegranate peel extract: A sustainable approach to bioactive delivery, Future Foods, Volume 11, 2025, 100560. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fufo.2025.100560	https://zenodo.org/records/14887507
4	2025	Tuning Properties of Sustainable Castor Oil Based Polyurethanes With Bacterial Biomass as Fillers	Journal of Polymers and the Environment	4.7	IMGGE	Rao, C.V., Guzik, M., Maslak, V. et al. Tuning Properties of Sustainable Castor Oil Based Polyurethanes With Bacterial Biomass as Fillers. J Polym Environ (2025). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-025-03540-5	https://zenodo.org/records/15267625

5	2025	Upcycling depolymerized PET waste into polyhydroxyalkanoates and triacylglycerols by a newly isolated Rhodococcus sp. strain	Biotechnology for the Environment	n.a. (new journal)	TUS	Rebocho, A.T., Torres, C.A., Koninckx, H. et al. Upcycling depolymerized PET waste into polyhydroxyalkanoates and triacylglycerols by a newly isolated Rhodococcus sp. strain. <i>Biotechnol Environ 2</i> , 5 (2025). https://doi.org/10.1186/s44314-025-00019-4	https://zenodo.org/records/15267466
6	2025	Upcycling PET plastic waste into bacterial nanocellulose based electro catalyst efficient in direct methanol fuel cells	Carbon Resources Conversion	7.1	IMGGE	Sanja Stevanovic, Jelena Milovanovic, Ramesh Babu Padamati, Vladan R. Cosovic, Dragana Milosevic, Christos Argirusis, Georgia Sourkouni, Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic, Marijana Ponjavic, Upcycling PET plastic waste into bacterial nanocellulose based electro catalyst efficient in direct methanol fuel cells, <i>Carbon Resources Conversion</i> , 2025, 100340, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crcon.2025.100340	https://zenodo.org/records/17191642
7	2025	Degradation of Biomaterials by Streptomyces microflavus DG19: Depolymerization Activity, Genome Mining and Soil Burial Assessment	Biotechnology for the Environment	n.a. (new journal)	IMGGE, TUS	Agapov, A., Pantelic, B., Ponjavic, M. et al. Degradation of biomaterials by <i>Streptomyces microflavus</i> DG19: depolymerization activity, genome mining, and soil burial assessment. <i>Biotechnol Environ 2</i> , 8 (2025). https://doi.org/10.1186/s44314-025-00024-7	https://zenodo.org/records/15781017
8	2025	Degradation of Synthetic and Natural Textile Materials Using Streptomyces Strains: Model Compost and Genome Exploration for Potential Plastic-Degrading Enzymes	Microorganisms	4.2	IMGGE	Janković, V.; Pantelic, B.; Ponjavic, M.; Marković, D.; Radetić, M.; Nikodinovic-Runic, J.; Ilic-Tomic, T. Degradation of Synthetic and Natural Textile Materials Using <i>Streptomyces</i> Strains: Model Compost and Genome Exploration for Potential Plastic-Degrading Enzymes. <i>Microorganisms</i> 2025, 13, 1800. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms13081800	https://zenodo.org/records/16811455

3.2.4. Media releases

EcoPlastiC project partners were hosted in **3** TV shows and **1** radio show during Y3. The list of media releases is shown in **Table 8.** and short description are provided below **Table 8.**

Table 8. List of articles and interviews given to the media in Y3

#	Partner institution	Type of media (name)	Presenters' name	Title and hyperlink
1	IMGGE	TV (RTV)	Brana Pantelic, Marijana Ponjavic	Science for the economy ("Nauka privredi")
2	IMGGE	Online TV (Ekovizija)	Jelena Milovanovic	"Green studio" ("Zeleni studio"): Microplastics
3	IMGGE	Radio (Radio Belgrade 2)	Ivana Aleksic	"I want to know" ("Hoću da znam")
4	IMGGE	TV (RTS1)	Brana Pantelic	"Science portal" ("Naučni portal")

1. Science for the economy on RTV

“In this episode, we spotlighted the **EcoPlastic** project, which is being implemented under the umbrella of the Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering at the University of Belgrade. The project centers on the recycling of mixed plastics and the development of high-performance biopolymers, with the goal of finding new applications for these materials through the course of the project.

EcoPlastic is part of the European “Pathfinder” program, which supports the journey from laboratory research to the commercialization of innovative solutions. Within this framework, researchers from the Institute, in collaboration with partners from Ireland, Belgium, Portugal, and Sweden have already made significant progress in advancing the technology. They have also identified new types of plastic waste that can be processed using the developed methods.”

2. “Green corner”: Microplastics

Jelena Milovanovic (IMGGE) participated in the “Green corner” show on Ekovizija (RTS Nauka), where the topic was microplastics! During the conversation, Jelena shared insights about our work in the EcoPlastiC project.

3. Radio Belgrade 2 – I want to know

On the occasion of World Environment Day, which has been celebrated since 1973 at the initiative of the United Nations, the topic discussed was how biotechnology can contribute to solving certain environmental problems.

Dr Ivana Aleksic from the Group for Eco-Biotechnology and Drug Development at the Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering in Belgrade talked about the projects currently being carried out within this research group. These projects aim to break down various types of plastic, produce biodegradable plastic materials, and even extract useful pharmaceuticals and bioactive compounds from plastic — all through the use of different microorganisms.

4. RTS – Science portal

The “Science portal” is a programme aired on Radio Television Serbia (RTS) that delivers a weekly dose of the most significant scientific discoveries, technology leaps, and innovations that change the future. “Old plastic bottle – new purpose” was the idea.

Dr Brana Pantelic showcased surprising solutions for items that we normally discard. From the landfills to the novel bio-materials and products, everything is possible with the help of bacteria!

3.2.5 Education and public engagement at partners’ institutes

During Y3 of the project, IMGGE, NOVA and AVE organised and participated in 6 public engagement visits and manifestations. The list of these activities is shown in **Table 9.** and short description are provided below **Table 9.**

Table 9. List of activities in Y3 focusing on education and public engagement

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	Career Day	IMGGE	Presenters	EcoPlastiC project	08/11/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	45

2	BioECOLOGics Talks: Bridging Ideas in Bioeconomy	IMGGE	Organiser & Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	15/11/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	48
3	Institute visit	IMGGE	Organiser	EcoPlastiC - from plastic waste to sustainable biopolymers using biotechnology	27/11/2024	Belgrade, Serbia	18
4	NOVA Science & Innovation Day	NOVA	Participant/presenter	Biopolymers Production	03/12/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	c.a. 150
5	Company visit	AVE	Presenters	EcoPlastiC project	04/04/2025	Ghent, Belgium	30
6	Practical course on Environmental Protection Studies	IMGGE	Presenters	EcoPlastiC project	24/04/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	19

1. IMGGE Career Day

A group of 45 students from the University of Nis visited IMGGE to learn about its organisation and operations. They were introduced to the work of the Group for Eco-Biotechnology and Drug Development and the waste-to-value concept. Additionally, they attended presentations on the group's current projects and had the opportunity to see advanced machinery like fermenters and LC-MS in action.

2. BioECOLOGics Talks: Bridging Ideas in Bioeconomy

This event was organized by IMGGE team as part of the BioECOLOGics project. It features the latest innovations in bioeconomy and explored ways to connect science with the industry. Speakers included experienced scientists from biotechnology laboratories and successful entrepreneurs who have transformed scientific ideas into creative industry solutions.

3. IMGGE institute visit

A group of students from the University of Nis (Serbia) visited IMGGE. The visit was organised under the title "IMGGE story - find your own IDEA" included presentations of all IMGGE research groups and most significant projects, followed by a tour of the institute.

4. NOVA Science & Innovation Day

This event was organized by NOVA university to present the excellent research carried out by the different units from NOVA University, as well as its impact on innovation and value creation for society. This event was got academic community and general public.

5. Avecom company visit

A group of students from Ghent University (Faculty of Bioscience Engineering) visited AVE. The visit started with a presentation of AVE followed by a tour in the company and a short introduction of the EcoPlastiC project.

6. Practical course on Environmental Protection Studies

A group of 19 students from the "Milutin Milanković" Geological and Hydrometeorological School visited IMGGE who presented ongoing projects, from innovative waste management to biotech solutions for a cleaner planet - it was a day full of learning, questions and inspiration.

3.2.6 School visits

During Y3 of the project, 17 school visits were organised and the concepts of biodegradable plastics, biopolymers, upcycling and other were explained. The list of school visits is shown in **Table 10**. and short description are provided below **Table 10**. The cooperation with the ToyStories project was prominent, an activity jointly done by TUS in Ireland and IMGGE in Serbia, which targeted young people aged 12-16 and used interactive workshops and creative activities to educate participants about the dangers of plastic waste and the importance of sustainability.

Table 10. List of school visits in Y3 where the EcoPlastiC project was presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	ToyStories I	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	01/10/2024	Cork, Ireland	28
2	ToyStories I	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	01/10/2024	Cork, Ireland	29
3	ToyStories I	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	08/10/2024	Dublin, Ireland	23

4	ToyStories I	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	09/10/2024	Portlaoise, Ireland	141
5	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	07/11/2024	Longford, Ireland	78
6	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	New Plastics for a New Generation	12/11/2024	Roscommon, Ireland	45
7	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	13/11/2024	Portlaoise, Ireland	141
8	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	18/11/2024	Kanturk, Ireland	57
9	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	19/11/2024	Cork, Ireland	28
10	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	19/11/2024	Cork, Ireland	29
11	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	26/11/2024	Dublin, Ireland	23
12	ToyStories II	TUS	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	28/11/2024	Dublin, Ireland	22
13	ToyStories II	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	22/11/2024	Vranje, Serbia	24
14	ToyStories II	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	26/11/2024	Novi Sad, Serbia	26
15	ToyStories II	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	29/11/2024	Pozarevac, Serbia	21
16	ToyStories II	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	06/12/2024	Kragujevac, Serbia	22
17	"What does a scientists do?"	IMGGE	Presenter	EcoPlastiC project	19/05/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	45

1-16. ToyStories

The ToyStories project was carried out in 12 elementary schools, 8 in Ireland and 4 in Serbia, and a comparative study and detailed statistical analysis is currently in progress.

In Ireland, the workshops were led by the project Principal Investigator Dr Marija Nicevic, along with associates Dr Eduardo Lanzagorta Garcia and Henrique Da Silva Pereira. Nearly every school had more than one group of students eager to participate in the project, and every professor expressed interest in continuing the collaboration beyond its initial scope. The second round of workshops was also incorporated into Science Week in 3 of the 8 participating schools, increasing the project's reach and reinforcing its impact by engaging even more students in discussions on plastic pollution and sustainability.

In Serbia, the research expanded to four schools in Novi Sad, Kragujevac, Požarevac and Vranje, further broadening the project's impact. The workshops were conducted by researchers from the Eco-Biotechnology

and Drug Development group at the Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering, University of Belgrade. The team, consisting of Dr Jelena Simic, Dr Sandra Vojnovic, Dr Ivana Aleksic, Vukasin Jankovic, Nikola Radivojevic and Dr Marijana Ponjavic, played a key role in delivering interactive sessions that educated students on plastic pollution, sustainability, and innovative solutions to environmental challenges.

17. "What does a scientist do?"

IMGGE was invited to Elementary School "Arcibald Rajs" to present the ongoing research and the EU projects, as well as to introduce the pupils to scientific work in the fields of biology and chemistry. EcoPlastiC project was presented to a pre-selected group of advance students between the fifth and the eighth grade.

3.2.7 Women in Science events

During Y3, 6 events were attended and organized by female team members from IMGGE, TUS and NOVA (**Table 11**) and their details are shown below **Table 11**.

Table 11. List of Women in Science events from Y3.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	Gender, Behaviour, and Decision-Making	IMGGE	Audience	Divergent Women (and Men)	03/12/2024	online	25
2	TUS Women's Network Speaker Series	TUS	Audience	Dr Catherine Cronin: Keynote Address on Open Education, Digital and Data Literacy	31/01/2025	Athlone, Ireland and online	15
3	International Day of Women and Girls in Science	IMGGE	Speaker	/	11/02/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	1700 followers on Instagram
4	2025 NOVA Global Women's Breakfast	NOVA	Audience	"Accelerating Equity in Science"	11/02/2025	Lisbon, Portugal	40
5	Public call for proposals to strengthen the	IMGGE	Audience and former Circular	"Reducing the Carbon Footprint of	05/03/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	62

	role of businesswomen in the circular economy - CIRCULAR AWARDS		Voucher Awardee	Local Communities by Applying the Principles of the Circular Economy in the Republic of Serbia – Circular Communities"			
6	EIC Women Leadership Programme	NOVA	Awardee	/	17/02-24/04/2025	online	/

1. Gender, Behaviour, and Decision-Making

The Women and Science Chair at Paris Dauphine-PSL University aims to mobilize and develop multidisciplinary approaches in order to analyze the determinants and impact of the low presence of women in scientific studies and careers. Renée Adams, Professor of Finance at Said Business School, University of Oxford, expert on corporate governance, bank governance and gender presented "Divergent Women (and Men)".

2. TUS Women's Network Speaker Series

The event provided valuable insights into the role of open education in fostering accessibility and equity in learning. Dr. Cronin's keynote address explored the significance of digital and data literacy in today's educational landscape, emphasizing how these competencies empower individuals to critically engage with digital information and contribute to an inclusive learning environment.

3. International Day of Women and Girls in Science

The International Day of Women and Girls in Science is celebrated annually on 11th of February. Today, women in science continue to push the boundaries of what is possible. IMGGI provides support to female scientists and all young girls who aspire to pursue science, because science knows no boundaries when it comes to talent, dedication, and passion.

4. 2025 NOVA Global Women's Breakfast

To celebrate diversity, equality and inclusion, NOVA FCT hosted the Global Women Breakfast (#GWB2025). The theme was "Accelerating Equity in Science", while 'Peace' was as a central element of the celebration, believing that peace is fundamental to promoting equity in science, diversity and inclusion. Professor Isabel Esteves provided a visual journey through five years of GWB's flagship images, sharing her creative process and reflections along the way.

5. Public call for proposals to strengthen the role of businesswomen in the circular economy - CIRCULAR AWARDS

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) announced that together with the Ministry of Environmental Protection of Serbia and with the support of the Global Environment Facility (GEF), they are opening a new public call for financial assistance to women entrepreneurs with innovative business models to strengthen the role of businesswomen in the circular economy. Companies, startups, agricultural enterprises and cooperatives, as well as social enterprises led by women, are invited to submit innovative solutions and business models that promote the principles and values of the circular economy in practice.

6. EIC Women Leadership Programme

To support the role of women in innovation and technology, the EIC - European Innovation Council, in partnership with the EIT - European Institute of Innovation and Technology, offers a skills enhancement and networking programme for women researchers and entrepreneurs, the EIC Women Leadership Programme. This is a tailored programme of trainings, networking, personal mentoring and business coaching.

3.2.8 Special sessions, forums and events organised by other EU Research Projects

Collaboration lies at the heart of EcoPlastiC’s mission to drive sustainable innovation across Europe. The project is deeply committed to building meaningful partnerships and actively participates in clustering activities that connect it with a wider network of EU-funded research initiatives. This interconnected approach is especially valuable, as many members of the EcoPlastiC consortium are already engaged in complementary European projects, bringing with them a wealth of experience and diverse perspectives.

By cultivating these cross-project relationships, EcoPlastiC not only amplifies the reach and relevance of its own research, but also contributes to a dynamic ecosystem of shared knowledge, mutual support, and collective progress. These strategic linkages enable the exchange of best practices, the pooling of resources, and the co-creation of innovative solutions that transcend individual project boundaries. In doing so, EcoPlastiC reinforces its position as a key contributor to the European research landscape, helping to shape a more integrated and impactful approach to tackling environmental challenges through biotechnology.

EcoPlastiC is actively participating in clustering activities and collaborating with other relevant EU research projects and initiatives, which is shown in **Table 12**. This is particularly important as several consortium members (TUS, IMGGE) are also involved in other EU-funded projects such as [TwInn4MicroUp](#) project.

“[EIC Pathfinder Beneficiaries Day](#)” took place on 20/11/2024 with EcoPlastiC representatives: Necdet Ozelik (TUS), Sandra Vojnovic (IMGGE), Kiran Reddy Baddigam (KTH) and Patricia Reis (NOVA). The event covered what it takes to translate a Pathfinder KER into a market-ready product or service, including intellectual property rights, value proposition development, business models, market analysis, team building, and navigating regulatory issues. The attendees learned more about all the available services to support the exploitation of Pathfinder results and on proactive project management.

Table 12. List of events organised by other EU-funded projects during Y3 where the EcoPlastiC project was presented.

#	Event name	Project partner	Role of the partner	Title of the presented work	Date	Location	Audience size
1	Fundamental Project Management Skills Workshop	IMGGE & TUS	Workshop attendees	EcoPlastiC project	14-15/10/2024	online	12
2	Effective Team Collaboration and Leadership	IMGGE	Workshop attendees	Leading WP6 of EcoPlastiC	11/06/2025	online	14
3	Advanced Administrative Skills for Project Managers	IMGGE	Workshop attendees	Leading WP6 of EcoPlastiC	24/07/2025	online	32
4	TwInn4MicroUp General Assembly	IMGGE	Attendee	DEC and DMP implementation: panel discussion	05/09/2025	Belgrade, Serbia	22

1. Fundamental Project Management Skills Workshop

The EcoPlastiC project was a key topic of discussion during the recent workshop organised by the TwInn4MicroUp project. This event brought together 12 selected participants from leading institution, NTUA, IMGGE, UNIBA and TUS. They explored critical topics such as regulation, reduction, upcycling and revalorisation of plastics. The EcoPlastiC project was selected as the joint initiative to base their discussions on because it aligns perfectly with these areas and reflects the ongoing work of many workshop attendees. <https://ecoplasticproject.eu/posts/building-on-a-shared-mission-ecoplastic-at-the-twinn4microup-workshop>

2. Effective Team Collaboration and Leadership

This was interactive and hands-on seminar that explore key aspects of leadership and collaboration in research project management. Through practical exercises and expert guidance, participants enhanced their leadership strategies, built stronger teams and refined their conflict resolution and communication skills. <https://twinn4microup.eu/2025/05/08/effective-team-collaboration-and-leadership-seminar/>

3. Advanced Administrative Skills for Project Managers

The seminar provided insights into consortium management, role distribution between coordinators and project managers and key frameworks for structuring Horizon Europe projects. Participants explored the characteristics of successful consortia, techniques for partner identification and stakeholder engagement through interactive exercises. Practical tools for project implementation, including Gantt charts, budget planning and risk management, were discussed alongside strategies for delivering impact through milestones and deliverables. <https://twinn4microup.eu/2025/07/15/advanced-administrative-skills-for-eu-project-managers-seminar/>

4. TwInn4MicroUp General Assembly

The EcoPlastiC team members from IMGGE and TUS participated in "Knowledge Transfer, Dissemination, and Outreach Activities" discussion session. Jelena Lazic, the EcoPlastiC WP6 coordinator, provided insights and know-how on the DEC and DMP implementation.

4. Indicators and targets - summary

Table 13 – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets

Channel/ Activity	Target number	Y1	Y2	Y3	Total
Website	Visits per year: <500 poor; 500-1000 good; >1000 excellent	1726 unique visitors	2059 unique visitors	1834 unique visitors	5619 unique visitors
Twitter	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	169 followers	356 followers	228 followers	
LinkedIn	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	104 followers	362 followers	562 followers	
Facebook	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	24 followers + 15 likes	38 followers + 19 likes	51 followers	
Instagram	Followers: <100 poor 100-200 good >200 excellent	166 followers	280 followers	354 followers	
Events	Attendances: <5 poor; 5-7 good; >7 excellent	8 events attended	15 events attended	16 events attended	39
Conferences	Attendances: <4 poor; 4-6 good; >6 excellent	6 conferences attended	16 conferences attended	24 conferences attended	46
Scientific publications	Published articles: <5 poor; 5-10 good; >10 excellent	1 publication	6 publications	8 publications	15
Media releases	Media: <4 poor 4-6 good >6 excellent	5 media releases	8 media releases	4 media releases	17

Education and public engagement at partners' institutes	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0 lectures/visit	3 lectures/visits	6 lectures/visits	9
School visits	Visits: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0 visits	16 visits	17 visits	33
Women in science events	Attendances: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	0 events	1 event	6 events	7
Special sessions, forums, events organised by other EU Research Initiatives	Engagements: <2 poor 2-4 good >4 excellent	1 participation	3 participations	4 participations	8

Over the course of the three years, the project demonstrated a clear pattern of gradual and consistent growth across nearly all communication channels and dissemination activities. In the initial year, several activities began at modest levels, but steady annual increases can be seen in most metrics, from social media followers to event participation and public engagements. By the final year, the majority of indicators had reached or exceeded their 'excellent' KPI thresholds, reflecting the effectiveness of the outreach strategy.

From the 5 communication channels and 8 dissemination/communication activities, 12 are performing with 'excellent' KPIs. There is only 1 channel that is in the 'poor' category. The number of followers on Facebook remains low, but this is due to the fact this social medium has lost its momentum and is not as popular as in the previous decade.

The progressive rise in website visits, X and LinkedIn engagement, conference and event attendance, and educational outreach activities illustrates a well-managed and well-targeted approach. Even activities that started from zero (such as school visits and women in science events) showed strong growth over time, surpassing their targets. This slow but steady progress confirms that dissemination and communication efforts were handled effectively, with sustained investment and adaptation leading to the achievement of the project's communication objectives.

5. Exploitation of the key project results

The EcoPlastiC project holds significant potential for exploitation of its results, not only by advancing scientific knowledge and its dissemination, but also by commercially capitalising on the EcoPlastiC innovation. To achieve this, a robust exploitation plan must be implemented, including appropriate activities and measures throughout the project's duration.

The initial concept of the exploitation plan was presented in the first version of DEC Plan delivered in M6 and the updated plan and presentation of the progress in the first year of project implementation was presented in M12 and M24. Based on the project proposal of the EcoPlastiC project, the project partners have previously defined the following key exploitable results (KERs) shown and explained in **Table 14**, with responsible partners and IP owners for each KER.

Table 14. EcoPlastiC Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

Key Exploitable Results (KERs)	Interest/Description	WPs	Responsible partner	IP owner(s)
KER1 – Green depolymerisation into constituent monomers as a new generation technology	To convert lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste to efficient polymer monomer and multimer fermentable feedstock for biopolymers and Eco-plastics by stream production processes from difficult to recycle post-use PET packaging and textile plastics.	WP2	TUS	TUS
KER2 – Enhanced and optimized Avecom microbiomes	To generate a value-added PHA biopolymer and other useful products by degradation and bioconversion of fermentable feedstock of waste plastic monomers and multimers.	WP3	AVE	AVE, NOVA
KER3 – Prototype PHA biopolymer materials	To develop and validate new PHA biopolymer materials focused on PHA, PHA3HV and other high performance copolymers, with performance properties equivalent to petroleum counterpart plastics, and extruded as potential future packaging plastics.	WP4	NOVA	NOVA, AVE, IMGGE
KER4 – Small-scale demonstrators of food packaging applications	To demonstrate EcoPlastiC innovation (new generation of recycling technology) to plastic value chain companies to produce high potential sustainable plastic products (by profile extrusion, blown film extrusion, thermoforming and injection moulding, cast film and vacuum forming).	WP5	KTH	KTH, TUS

Main elements of exploitation strategy and appropriate measures to be implemented are structured for each key exploitable results as follows:

- Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description
- **Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation**
- Technical innovation (short description)
- Main competitive advantage(s)
- **KER protection (IPR measures)**
- **Target sector(s)**
- **Early adopters**
- **Target users**
- **Primary market**
- **Market barriers**
- **Communication & dissemination measures**
- Expected impact
- **Further steps to scaling-up**

Updated individual exploitation strategies for KERs are presented in Annex I of this Report. Some of the elements of the strategy are interesting for monitoring and reporting during the project (written in **bold** font), so in Table A1 are summarized progress for key results related to the already presented dissemination and communication measures implemented during the second year of the project.

In addition, throughout the project, EIC Innovation Radar questionnaire was regularly updated and EcoPlastiC innovations are presented in **Annex III**.

Table 15. KER1 exploitation progress (responsible TUS)

KER1	Green depolymerisation into constituent monomers as a new generation technology	Progress in the third year (short description and measurable indicators)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	Preparation For Spin out with entrepreneurship team identified and business plan completed.	In partnership with the Novelplast , the scale-up process began in Year 1, and initial results indicate its success. The TPA monomer has been produced at high yields from a number of waste PET streams including coloured PET/PE and metallised PET. Additionally, collaboration interest with ALPEK has been identified. A full business plan has been prepared and investment is being sought
KER protection (IPR measures)	Patent application.	UK Patent Application No: 2116474.4. International Patent Application No: PCT/EP2022/082101.
Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plastic/plastic waste producing industries • Packaging industries • Waste treatment industries 	Leading producer of PTA & PET has been targeted in Year 1.
Early adopters	ALPEK polyesters, NOVELPLAST, Avaencourt	Scale up experiments have been successfully conducted at Krauss Maffie and further investment is required to progress to the next stage
Target users/Primary market	Plastic producing companies/Packaging companies/Waste treatment facilities	New collaboration with ALPEK is being explored.
Market barriers	Technological readiness TRL6	Actively working with NovelPlast and Avoncourt to secure investment to deliver scaled up operation.
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.	<p>TUS Research week (poster presentation). Presentation to TUS company clients.</p> <p>Margaret Brennan Fournet, visited Eli Lilly at their Limerick facility. Eli Lilly announced a significant expansion of their manufacturing operations, with a €1 billion investment in Ireland aimed at</p>

	Encourage on-going two-way dialogue between the consortium and industry stakeholders.	increasing the production of biologic active ingredients for global disease treatment—an important focus area for LIFE RI. Margaret Brennan Fournet spoke with the Mayor of Limerick, John Moran, and Kieran O'Donnell TD, Minister of State for the Office of Public Works, about the collaborative work undertaken across TUS research, development, and LIFE RI.
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5 at the end of the project's Year 1. Expected TRL: 6-7, towards the end of the project.	Current TRL: 4-5

KER1A	High Gas barrier packaging ¹ (a least equivalent to petro-based Ethylene vinyl alcohol (EVOH))	Progress in the second year (short description and measurable indicators)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	KTH and TUS are actively developing High Gas barrier packaging (a least equivalent to petro-based Ethylene vinyl alcohol (EVOH) O ₂ barrier 0.4 [cm ² .mm/(m ² .24h.atm)]), using microbial protein (MP) and polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) layered films and trays	Layered films and trays identified for prototype developments including supermarket precooked food, bag-in-box wines and other beverages, dairy products/cheese, bake-up bread and meat products such as trays and film wrapping for meat maturation (The layered structure enabling use as translucent packaging for UV-sensitive food products.
KER protection (IPR measures)	Know-How and In-house Microbial Strains	Newly validated for high performance barrier properties combined with full circularity and high potential LCA metrics
Target sector(s)	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	Commercialisation Feasibility (CFF) study engaging with 21 no of companies as given in the Table in Annex II . The aim of CFF was to gather industry perspectives on the potential of CicloPak and CicloSeal in replacing conventional plastic-based materials with bio-based, compostable, and

¹ <https://innovation-radar.ec.europa.eu/innovation/54123>

		recyclable alternatives, focusing on key performance requirements. Many expressed willingness to support testing, provide samples, share technical data, and in some cases offer letters of support for funding, underlining both strong market interest and the need for further validation (Table in Annex II).
Early adopters	Meat industry, Supermarket Food suppliers	Potential being explored with companies such as Zeus Packaging, LogoPlaste, TetraPack, Dawn Meats, Lactips Amcor and Kerry Group
Target users/Primary market	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	Zeus Packaging, LogoPlaste, TetraPack, Dawn Meats, Lactips Amcor and Kerry Group
Market barriers	Bio-refineries are emerging and are not yet widely available Regulatory requirements for food contact approval and compostability certification	Submitted EIC Transition proposal for Scale up to bring to TRL 6-7 (see Table A4 in Annex I for more details).
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.	TUS Research week (poster presentation). Presentation to TUS company clients
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5, towards the end of the project's Year 3.	Current TRL: 4

KER1B	Bioadhesives for paper cups and plastic packaging sealant prototypes with equivalent performance to conventional synthetic adhesives.	Progress in the second year (<i>short description and measurable indicators</i>)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	TUS are actively developing Bioadhesives with adhesion values approaching commercial Prittstick and Superglue.	Bioadhesives for paper & plastic packaging sealant prototypes using enhanced MP

KER protection (IPR measures)	Know-How and In-house Microbial Strains Invention Disclosure Form in preparation for submission	Newly validated for high performance adhesion combined with full circularity and high potential LCA metrics
Target sector(s)	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	/
Early adopters	Meat industry, Supermarket Food suppliers	Potential being explored with companies such as Benders Paper Cups Flo Group, CupPrint / Huhtamäki, Eva-Tek DAC
Target users/Primary market	Food Packaging value chain and related stakeholders	Benders Paper Cups Flo Group, CupPrint / Huhtamäki, Eva-Tek DAC, Irish Bioeconomy Foundation (IBF), Limerick Polymers Production, NPP Ireland
Market barriers	Biorefineries are emerging and are not yet widely available	Submitted EIC Transition proposal for Scale up to bring to TRL 6-7
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.	TUS Research week (poster presentation). Presentation to TUS company clients
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5, towards the end of the project's Year 3.	Current TRL: 4 next steps required include : Validation of functionality, application compatibility, and performance in real production environments. Establishment of technical collaborations with formulation and materials specialists such as va-Tek DAC

Table 16. KER2 exploitation progress (responsible AVE, NOVA)

KER2	Enhanced and optimized Avecom microbiomes	Progress in the second year (<i>short description and measurable indicators</i>)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	AVE and NOVA will disseminate the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in industry events and	AVE hosted a webinar in which EcoPlastiC was represented and presented the project in several events (see Table 5).

	conferences where there is potential to network, hold exhibition stands, to secure further collaborations, research contracts, or licensing deals.	NOVA developed a mixed microbial consortium for TPA upcycling into PHA which was validated by AVE. NOVA isolated two enhanced microbes (strains 24A and DM-14) that can efficiently convert TPA into single cell protein and PHA. NOVA participated in several conferences/events where these results were disseminated. A new research European project, UPSTREAM (GA: 101112877), was initiated where NOVA will collaborate with VITO (Belgium), Tecnopackaging (Spain) and the National Institute of Chemistry (Slovenia) in the production of PHA from plastics recovered from rivers. NOVA also participated in two proposals: ME4BIO coordinated by the Universidad de Alicante (Spain) submitted to the HORIZON-CL6-2024-CIRCBIO-01 call; and BIO2VALUE, coordinated by the ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION (Greece) submitted to the HORIZON-CL6-2024-CircBio-02-6-two-stage - From silos to diversity – small-scale bio-based demonstration pilots call. For these projects/proposals, the know-how of PHA production and plastic biodegradation obtained by NOVA in the EcoPlastiC project was essential.
KER protection (IPR measures)	No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.	All obtained results are confidential (know-how secret).
Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste treatment industries • PHA producing companies • Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive 	
Early adopters	Waste collecting industries: they could use this technology not only to recycle plastic but to valorise and upgrade their plastic	

	waste to a raw material that can be used for the production of valuable products or possibly eco-plastics.	
Target users/Primary market	<p>The following potential customers were identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solid Waste treatment / collecting utilities operators (domestic / industrial general waste). • Plastic recycling operators (domestic / industrial sorted waste). • Plastic industry (scraps waste, monomer(s) waste, etc). • Industries generating plastic waste (treating waste in situ). • Packaging industry 	
Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness	Working with mixed cultures has the potential of reducing the production cost.
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events, organising visits for potential investors and/or B2B to the demo plant	AVE hosted a webinar in which EcoPlastiC was represented and presented the project at several events (see Table 5). Contribution to one paper in collaboration with KTH.
Further steps to scaling-up	At the end of EcoPlastiC project, AVE reached TRL3-4 and NOVA's isolates reached TRL 2-3.	AVE is looking for upcoming calls to take the results further towards TRL5-6 and above. Within the UPSTREAM project, NOVA will further optimize this technology towards TRL 4-5.

Table 17. KER3 exploitation progress (responsible NOVA, IMGGE)

KER3	Prototype PHA biopolymer materials	Progress in the second year (<i>short description and measurable indicators</i>)
<p>Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation</p>	<p>NOVA will disseminate the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in conferences where there is potential to network, to secure further collaborations and new research contracts. IMGGE will also disseminate through scientific publications and conferences and direct contact with commercial stakeholders.</p>	<p>NOVA developed films based on PHA-rich and protein-rich biomasses with enhanced barrier and mechanical properties.</p> <p>NOVA participated in several conferences/events where these results were disseminated. Moreover, two publications are planned and currently being written. NOVA's expertise in the development of novel PHA-based materials resulted in the participation in two proposals recently submitted for European funding opportunities: PHAbble, as coordinators, submitted to the HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDEROPEN call; FERTINOVA, coordinated by France's National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment, submitted to the HORIZON-JU-CBE-2025-RIA-02 call; and RENEW submitted to the Water4All 2024 Joint Transnational Call on "Water for Circular Economy". Also, NOVA secured funding from Banco de Portugal for a project (€coCard) that aims at using residues to produce high-performing PHA-based materials.</p> <p>At IMGGE, 3 new PHA-based blends were prepared. One of the blends has been described in "Double layer bacterial nanocellulose - poly(hydroxyoctanoate) film activated by prodigiosin as sustainable, transparent, UV-blocking material" (https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.135087), One blend with enhanced properties, represents the base of bio-polyurethane is being evaluated as novel material.</p> <p>The third blend has been developed in collaboration with Sfericon SME and the prototypes are being developed.</p>
<p>KER protection (IPR measures)</p>	<p>No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.</p>	
<p>Target sector(s)</p>	<p>PHA producing companies</p>	

	Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive sectors	
Early adopters	Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive sectors	
Target users/Primary market	Packaging Industry	
Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness	
Communication & dissemination measures	<p>Conferences, peer-reviewed scientific journals, social media, workshops and fairs.</p> <p>Organising visits for potential investors and/or B2B to the demo plant.</p>	<p>IMGGE organised meetings with several companies:</p> <p><u>Sferikon</u> https://www.sferikon.com/</p> <p>Sferikon is a young company developing new biomaterials made out of corn stover and blends as a sustainable alternative to plastic. Following the vision that every material in the nature is created with purpose and efficiency, Sferikon perfectly meets with the circularity goals. IMGGE team established the collaboration with this company in designing and creating the prototypes of PHA based composites reinforced with corn stover for specific purposes, but also this collaboration resulted in the designed prototype of PHA based bio 3D shoes.</p> <p><u>SOLFINS</u> https://solfins.com/</p> <p>SOLFINS company is leading industry solutions providers and partners for 500+ product development and manufacturing companies, offering consulting and expertise, product development, technology and machines, engineering services, additive manufacturing, etc. One of the activities recognized of the great collaborative potential is 3D printing of biopolymers and co-creation opportunities resulting in the innovative</p>

customized formulations. The IMGGE representatives introduced the research activity of the team, and gained interest of Solfins to participate in joint HE applications.

BIOPLASTECH

<https://www.bioplastech.com/>

Bioplastech Ltd. specialise in the development, scale-up and sale of innovative bio-based products including biodegradable polymers (PHAs). Bioplastech also provides industrial biotechnological consulting services supporting customers in the development, improvement and scale-up of their biological processes. Constructive discussions with the Bioplastech representatives are under way, for optimisation of PHA production scale-up from difficult carbon sources, such as monomers and oligomers from plastic depolymerisation processes.

IKEA

<https://www.ikea.com/rs/sr/>

IKEA is one of the most iconic and influential global brands in the home furnishings industry—known not just for its flat-pack furniture and minimalist Scandinavian design, but for reshaping how people live, shop, and think about sustainability. It has over 480 locations across 63 countries, including Serbia, as of 2025. Supporting sustainability & innovation concept, IKEA aims to become climate positive by 2030, focusing on renewable & recycled materials in products, circular services like furniture buy-back and repair, investments in clean energy and sustainable forestry. IMGGE team members visited IKEA branch in Serbia aiming to present the work and activities in the area of developing new biotechnological routes in synthetic plastic and textile degradation, aligning with the IKEA's future sustainable goals and circularity. IKEA's representatives showed interest in PHAs, but also in development of the routes from PU materials to biopolymers.

		<p><u>POLYHEDRA</u> https://www.polyhedra.co/en/homepage/ POLYHEDRA is a design and engineering company focusing on creating innovative and functional products, transferring ideas from concept to reality, but also provides 3D printing and prototyping services efficiently bridging ideas to life. The cutting-edge technology available in this company allows it to produce high-quality prototypes, giving a better idea of how the prototypes will function in the real world. The meeting was an excellent chance for the IMGGE team to introduce the ongoing projects, including EcoPlastiC, to share the ideas and perspectives for the potential collaboration through the projects in the future and to discuss about the potential of biopolymers in 3D printing.</p> <p><u>CIREKON</u> https://cirekon.rs/ CirEkon company drives the transition to a circular economy by fostering innovation, sustainable business practices, and responsible marketing. Through collaboration, CirEkon creates innovative business models that meet the evolving demands of circular markets. At the organized meeting between IMGGE EcoPlastiC representatives and CEO of CirEkon company, Milan Veselinov, the great potential for the collaboration in the future, through product-service lifecycle management, following the principles of circular economy and sustainable development, has been discussed.</p> <p><u>ECO BIO CROATIA</u> https://ecobiocro.com/ Eco Bio® Croatia developed a new biopolymer that is environment friendly, non-toxic alternative to flexible, usually single use plastic. The collaboration has been established in terms of investigation of biodegradability of new biomaterial, but also this company participated in</p>
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		<p>HE consortium for number of applications. This company showed interest in PHAs and possibility to create blends with their own proprietary biomaterial.</p> <p><u>OXMAN</u> https://oxman.com/</p> <p>Oxman is a pioneering company where design, technology, and biology converge to shape the future of innovation. They are focusing on creating multi-scale products and environments by reimagining the boundaries between hardware, software, and wetware. Through radical thinking and making, the main challenges are uncovering new knowledge and take on challenges - design drives scientific discovery, and science expands the possibilities of design. The interdisciplinary approach results in fusion of atelier, workshop, and laboratory. The initial meeting with Oxman's representative occurred during ISBP2024, where they introduced innovative processing of PHAs, then the meeting was followed-up with several on-line discussions about PHAs, and possible addition of biomass fillers.</p> <p><u>JUB d.o.o.</u> https://www.jub.rs/</p> <p>JUB d.o.o. is the Serbian branch of the internationally recognized JUB Group, one of the oldest manufacturers of wall paints and construction coatings in the region, located in Šimanovci, Serbia. JUB d.o.o. plays a key role in the group's regional operations, contributing to both production and distribution across South-eastern Europe. JUB d.o.o. Serbia is part of a broader network that includes six production plants—three in Slovenia and three in Serbia—and has recently become part of the Nippon Paint Holdings Group, expanding its global reach and innovation potential. Main activities of the JUB d.o.o. company are - production of decorative and protective coatings including interior wall paints, facade systems,</p>
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		<p>waterproofing solutions, and coatings for wood, metal, and concrete surfaces; development of integrated façade systems such as the JUBIZOL system, which enhances energy efficiency and promotes healthier living environments. The meeting organized with the head of R&D department, Dr Milos Tomic, where both sides introduced the projects and activities, express the interest for bio-pigments, bacterial products available at IMGGE. The collaboration was extended through the projects applications and innovative projects.</p> <p><u>OUTLANDER MATERIALS</u> https://www.outlandermaterials.com/</p> <p>Outlander Materials is a clean biotech company based in Rotterdam, Netherlands, known for its approach to sustainable materials - revalorizes waste by using it to create new materials that are compostable, getting closer to the vision of a circular and sustainable future. Their flagship innovation, UnPlastic, is a compostable, non-toxic, and non-plastic alternative to single-use packaging—engineered from food industry by-products, especially beer brewery waste. The material biodegrades without releasing micro- or nanoplastics, making it ideal for circular economy applications in packaging, food safety, and environmental design. This company contacted us based on the web-site visit and they initiated discussion regarding PHA processing and combinations with BNC.</p>
<p>Further steps to scaling-up</p>	<p>At the end of EcoPlastiC project, it is estimated to reach TRL3-4. If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years. TRL6-7 could be achieved after another 2-4 years. Thus, the time to market could be between 7-10 years.</p>	<p>Current TRL is 3.</p>

Table 18. KER4 exploitation progress (responsible KTH)

KER4	Small-scale demonstrators of food packaging applications	Progress in the second year (<i>short description and measurable indicators</i>)
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	KTH (with TUS) will lead the development of high-performance eco-plastics blends and single/multilayers for food packaging applications (flexible packaging and trays). Replacement of fossil-based plastics into PHA enriched eco-plastics and microbial/single-cell bio-plastics.	WP5 started at M24 and the progress regarding demonstrators for food packaging applications has been described in the following reporting periods/deliverables as well as in several publications (one accepted already).
KER protection (IPR measures)	The outcome results will be discussed within the consortium and published in scientific journals. If any breakthrough results find, that may be patented.	No patent-filing currently. Two publications are currently in preparation and one is accepted.
Target sector(s)	Plastic producers, packaging companies in the food sector, food producers and retailers	
Early adopters	Food packaging industries could be in the first row to adopt our eco-friendly biopolymer as alternative to fossil-based plastics.	
Target users/Primary market	Packaging producers, food producers and retailers	
Market barriers	Food packaging approval, logistics	
Communication & dissemination measures	International conference participation, Laboratory tours to design smart equipment, webinar talks to enhance the network in packaging sector, motivate youth towards the eco-friendly science projects by showcasing our new eco-plastic	We have had communications with Graphic Packaging International and Tetra Pak on SCP/PHA materials. One publication is accepted and two are under preparation for SCP films/trays, SCP/biopolymer blends and multilayer films. Part of the work has been communicated at an invited presentation at the 44th

	prototype products. Publication in scientific journals.	Frontier Scientists Workshop in Stockholm, 2023, an invited presentation at the University of PISA, 2024, and a keynote lecture at the EP25 conference in Harbin, China in 2025.
Further steps to scaling-up	At the end of EcoPlastiC project, we reach TRL3-4. If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years.	We will seek for upcoming calls to take the results further towards TRL5-6 and above.

6. Conclusions

This report **D6.8** provided an overview of the dissemination, exploitation and communication work carried out in the third and final year on the EcoPlastiC project, from 1st October 2024 – 30th September 2025. It summaries the main activities of all partners, which were systematically organised and presented by IMGGE, the project partner leading WP6 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication. It is based on the detailed **D6.1** Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (M6), which provided a framework to communicate our project activities and disseminate project results, and it is a continuation of the **D6.3** First annual report on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities and **D6.7** Second annual report on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities.

During Y3, EcoPlastiC project partners participated in 16 events, 17 conferences (24 contributions), they published 8 papers, had 4 media releases, organised a total of 6 education and public engagements, 17 school visits, participated in 6 women in science event and were invited to take part in 4 events organised by other EU research initiatives. Furthermore, during Y3, numerous visits for potential investors and B2B meetings were successfully organized, especially by TUS and IMGGE.

In its final year, the EcoPlastiC project demonstrated a strategic and impactful approach to dissemination, exploitation and communication. Through coordinated efforts led by IMGGE, WP6 activities reached thousands of stakeholders across academia, industry, education and the wider public. From scientific conferences and media outreach to investor engagement and EU project collaborations, the project’s visibility and influence were significantly amplified. These results reflect the consortium’s commitment to ensuring that EcoPlastiC’s innovations resonate beyond the lab, driving awareness, uptake and long-term impact across Europe and beyond.

ANNEX I – KER market-oriented exploitation progress

Table A1. KER1 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible TUS)

KER1	Green depolymerisation into constituent monomers as a new generation technology
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	Mechano-green strategies developed at TUS aim to combine a range of polymer treatments (ultrasonication, UV degradation, microwave treatment and reactive extrusion) to close the loop of mixed plastic waste management by allowing the depolymerization of materials to source new monomers for the production of virgin PET and produce the feedstock for the manufacture of new biobased and biodegradable materials. Outcomes will be disseminated through conferences, scientific publications, reports, and social media channels. Patent regarding this technology has been submitted.
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	Further optimisation and upgrading of existing technology will be conducted at TUS. Communication with industry sector and other research facilities in order to up-scale and boost efficiency of the process will be implemented.
Technical innovation (short description)	<p>A method for processing polyester plastic waste material, such as post-consumer polyethylene terephthalate waste material, using hot-melt extrusion of the plastic waste material in the presence of a depolymerisation agent and a plasticising agent comprising one or more inorganic salts.</p> <p>UK Patent Application No: 2116474.4. International Patent Application No: PCT/EP2022/082101.</p>
Main competitive advantage(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a continuous recycling technology for all grades of PET – spanning pristine bottle grades to low grade PET pots and trays. • Significant contribution towards halting resource depletion, landfilling and incineration of waste plastics instead converting them into valuable resources and demonstrating the implementation of a circular plastic model.
KER protection (IPR measures)	As mentioned before, part of this research is already in the process of Patent submission.

Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plastic/plastic waste producing industries • Packaging industries • Waste treatment industries
Early adopters	ALPEK polyesters, NOVELPLAST, Avencourt
Target users/Primary market	Plastic producing companies/Packaging companies/Waste treatment facilities
Market barriers	Technological readiness
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events.
Expected impact	Making a substantial impact in the effort to combat resource depletion, reduce the disposal of plastics in landfills and incineration, and instead, transforming waste plastics into valuable resources while showcasing the practical application of a circular plastic economy.
Further steps to scaling-up	Current TRL: 4-5, towards the end of the project's Y1. Expected TRL: 6-7, towards the end of the project.

Table A2. KER2 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible AVE, NOVA)

KER2	Enhanced and optimized AVE microbiomes
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	The knowledge generated on optimization of microbiomes and production of biopolymer would be disseminated to scientific community, industry sector, government, environmental NGOs and civil society of progress that is being made in the field of environmental monitoring. The key parameters of the pilot - process parameters, scientific and technical know-how, design, maintenance, production and engineering - of the technology for the production of the bio-product will be protected as a trade secret. Exploitation intentions are either manufacturing a bioproduct, either licensing to industry.
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	AVE and NOVA disseminated the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in industry events and conferences where there is potential to network, hold exhibition stands, to secure further collaborations, research contracts, or licensing deals. NOVA disseminated the exploitable results of the project by participating in several conferences and events. As a result of these participations, successfully secured further collaborations and new research contracts that will ensure the future development of this technology.

Technical innovation (short description)	The result of the project will be a solution for mixed plastic pollution. ECOPLASTIC converts lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers, through the development of a suite of breakthrough modular and technologies adaptable to the waste input and provides next generation technology to funnel waste PET plastics into Eco-products.
Main competitive advantage(s)	In case bio-plastic production is possible, this KER will become a key to turn a linear process of plastic into a circular economy.
KER protection (IPR measures)	No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.
Target sector(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste treatment industries • PHA producing companies • Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive
Early adopters	Waste collecting industries: they could use this technology not only to recycle plastic but to valorise and upgrade their plastic waste to a raw material that can be used for the production of valuable products or possibly a eco-plastics.
Target users/Primary market	<p>The following potential customers were identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solid Waste treatment / collecting utilities operators (domestic / industrial general waste). • Plastic recycling operators (domestic / industrial sorted waste). • Plastic industry (scraps waste, monomer(s) waste, etc). • Industries generating plastic waste (treating waste in situ). • Packaging industry
Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness
Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, symposia, workshops, special sessions, forums and events, organising visits for potential investors and/or B2B to the demo plant. Participation in one publication with KTH.
Expected impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • less (micro) plastic might contaminate soil/water and newer biodegradable plastic would naturally decompose. • it is expected that the CO2 emissions of the newer biodegradable plastic would be lower.

Further steps to scaling-up	<p>At the end of EcoPlastiC project, AVE reached TRL3-4 and NOVA reached TRL 2-3. AVE is looking for upcoming calls to take the results further towards TRL5-6 and above. In the recently secured research contract, NOVA will further optimize the technology towards TRL 4-5. If successful, it can be estimated to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years. TRL6-7 could be achieved after another 2-4 years. Thus, the time to market could be between 7-10 years.</p>
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Table A3. KER3 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible NOVA, IMGGE)

KER3	Prototype PHA biopolymer materials
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	The knowledge generated on PHA biopolymer materials will be disseminated to scientific community and plastic industry sector. The scientific and technical know-how will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals (at least two publications are under preparation).
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	NOVA disseminated the exploitable outputs of EcoPlastiC project by participating in conferences where there is potential to network, to secure further collaborations and new research contracts.
Technical innovation (short description)	PHA biopolymer materials (focused on PHB, PHBHV and other high performance copolymers) and protein-based materials, with performance properties equivalent to petroleum counterpart plastics, and extruded as potential future packaging plastics.
Main competitive advantage(s)	Biodegradability of the produced materials while ensuring high performance.
KER protection (IPR measures)	No patent application is planned. The results will be protected by trade secret.
Target sector(s)	PHA producing companies Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive
Early adopters	Packaging Companies in the textile, medical textile, automotive
Target users/Primary market	Packaging Industry
Market barriers	Production cost, Technological readiness

Communication & dissemination measures	Conferences, peer-reviewed scientific journals, social media, workshops and fairs.
Expected impact	less (micro) plastic might contaminate soil/water and newer biodegradable plastic would naturally decompose. it is expected that the CO2 emissions of the newer biodegradable plastic would be lower.
Further steps to scaling-up	At the end of EcoPlastiC project, NOVA reached TRL3. If successful in the recently submitted proposals, NOVA expects to reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years. TRL6-7 could be achieved after another 2-4 years. Thus, the time to market could be between 7-10 years.

Table A4. KER4 Market-oriented exploitation approach (responsible KTH, TUS)

KER4	Small-scale demonstrators of food packaging applications
Partner(s) interest in the exploitation (low, medium or high), with short description	High, partners have interest in going forward with the concept explored here. The materials produced have the potential to compete with fossil-based plastics in several applications, not the least in the packaging sector.
Partner(s) role in KER development and its exploitation	KTH has led the development of high-performance eco-plastics blends and single/multilayers (flexible packaging and trays) for food packaging applications. TUS will contribute by developing microbial protein-based films and adhesives, and by co-developing multilayer demonstrators (PHA + protein) that are tested for barrier and sealing performance. Replacement of fossil-based plastics into PHA enriched eco-plastics and microbial/single-cell bio-plastics.
Technical innovation (short description)	Producing bioplastics from PET waste through the development of multilayer food packaging demonstrators combining PHA and microbial proteins, which achieved oxygen barrier properties comparable to EVOH and good water resistance validated at lab scale
Main competitive advantage(s)	First demonstration of bio-based multilayers with EVOH replacement potential, combining high oxygen barrier properties from proteins with the water resistance of PHAs, while enabling fully plastic-free, compostable sealants and films
KER protection (IPR measures)	The outcome results are discussed within the consortium and are presented in one accepted article, and in several manuscripts to be published. Currently no patents have been filed.
Target sector(s)	Plastic producers, packaging companies in the food sector, food producers and retailers

Early adopters	Food packaging industries could be in the first row to adopt our eco-friendly biopolymer as alternative to fossil-based plastics.
Target users/Primary market	Plastics producers, Packaging producers, Recycling sector in Plastics, Food producers and retailers
Market barriers	Food-contact regulatory approval, need for pilot-scale lamination equipment
Communication & dissemination measures	International conference participation, Laboratory tours to design smart equipment, webinar talks to enhance the network in packaging sector, motivate youth towards the eco-friendly science projects by showcasing our new eco-plastic prototype products. Publications in scientific journals. Market validation disseminated via CFF study (CicloPak/CicloSeal), targeting brand owners and packaging producers
Expected impact	The plasticized PHA and Microbial protein biopolymers have the potential to replace fossil-based multilayer packaging, reduce plastic waste and provide compostable alternatives that support EU Circular Economy goals, while contributing to broader environmental objectives such as life-on-land, and life-below-water.
Further steps to scaling-up	At the end of EcoPlastiC project, we have reached TRL3-4. If successful, it may reach TRL5-6 within 5-6 years.

Annex II – CicloPak and CicloSeal - Company Feedback Overview (TUS)

No.	Company name	Contact person	Feedback on CicloPak	Feedback on CicloSeal	Overall feedback
1	ABP Food Group 	John Durkan (Environmental & Sustainability Manager)	Biggest opportunity in intermediate packaging (primal bags for storage/transfer), with potential for closed-loop return/remake. Retailers will consider packaging change if cheaper. In needs for multilayer or multi-bag packaging; must maximise shelf life and colour stability by limiting oxygen and bacteria growth.	Not specifically mentioned.	Positive- very open to an exclusive arrangement for a year.
2	Benders Paper Cups (Flo Group) 	Allan Paterson (Technical & Development Manager)	Not specifically mentioned, general interest in novel materials.	Saw CicloSeal as potential plastic-free bio-adhesives alternative, if proven to meet both EU Single Use Plastics Directive (SUPD) compliance and plastic-free criteria. Being able to make credible “100% sustainable” claims would be a strong market differentiator.	Positive- offered to supply board samples, share process timing details, prepared to engage over an 18-month or longer development horizon.

3	<p>BWG Foods UC</p>	Megan Kelly (ESG Manager)	Environmental, Social, and Corporate Governance (ESG) and regulatory drivers may accelerate adoption. A small premium tolerance 10–20% might be paid for a more sustainable packaging solution.	Not specifically mentioned.	Neutral
4	<p>Camvac</p>	Gary Chalkley (Technical Manager), Maria Del Valle Arenas (Quality & Technical Manager), James Shipman (Process Development Manager)	Interested in depolymerisation process of metallised PET via CicloPak process; could aid shift to mono-materials. Would be of interest if CicloPak can achieve with oxygen barrier performance under 1cc/m ² /day, thicknesses (ideally 12–36 microns), and able to withstand mechanical and production stresses.	A potential opportunity for bio-based adhesives with built-in oxygen barrier, benefit efforts to laminate biomaterials and create compostable structures.	Positive- could supply samples of their metallized materials for further testing, offer metallising CicloPak on their pilot line, providing tensile and modulus data from existing products, and continuing dialogue.
5	<p>Cup Print</p>	Terry Fox (Founder & GM)	Very interested if CicloPak/CicloSeal qualifies as an “unmodified natural polymer” under SUPD.	Sees strong potential if CicloSeal can achieve waterproofing, oxygen barrier, and could be extruded, applied as films,	Positive- willing to support testing and access commercial extrusion lines.

			Encouraged a review of relevant IP and patent landscapes, particularly around the use of PHA-based coatings.	and heat-sealed effectively ($\geq 160^{\circ}\text{C}$).	
6	<p>Eva-Tec DAC</p>	Joe English (Chairman)	Not specifically mentioned.	<p>Stressed need for the bio-adhesives that can deliver comparable application speed, processability, and performance at industrial scale.</p> <p>Key requirements: maintain integrity at -40°C, fast application speed, compostability without interfering with recycling.</p>	Positive- offer letter of support for funding.
7	<p>Frugalpac</p>	John-Paul Grogan (Product Director)	Requires strict performance on pouch (drop performance & barrier), weldability, and organoleptic neutrality standards.	Not specifically mentioned.	Positive- openness to testing new materials, particularly if they can match the technical criteria.
8	<p>Huhtamaki</p>	Rohit Subramanian (Venturing Manager)	Interested in oxygen barrier innovations. Identifying materials that meet regulatory compliance, such as SUPD and PPWR in EU and BPI, recyclability,	Clear interest in plastic-free adhesives; biodegradable and compostable adhesives, particularly in flexible packaging.	Positive- willingness to test or pilot new materials but said that internal benchmarking would be needed.

			composability in North America.		
9	<p>Irish Bioeconomy Foundation (IBF)</p>	Stephen Napier (CEO)	Supports TUS collaboration and pilot/demo facilities in fermentation for CicloPak and CicloSeal production	Not specifically mentioned.	Positive -welcomed the idea of building a future project into the Lisheen facility pipeline (2026 timing suitable), offered a site visit
10	<p>Limerick Polymers Production (LPP)</p>	Mark Sheahan (General Manager)	Offered perspective on the potential for integrating CicloPak materials into the current mixed waste processing system. Feasibility depends on qualify as “recycled” under existing EPR (Extended Producer Responsibility) schemes.	Not specifically mentioned.	Positive - providing a letter of support for funding applications to Enterprise Ireland’s Commercialisation Fund.
11	<p>Magfi</p>	Filippo Giancarlo (Founder)	Offered guidance on how the CicloPak/CicloSeal team might engage with IBF, to connect with Stephen Napier (CEO) and Sean O’Grady for future pilot scale work.	Not specifically mentioned.	Positive – Encouraged ongoing contact for alignment and EU initiatives; stressed need for a distinctive application for long-term success.
12	<p>Musgrave Group</p>	Owen Keogh (Head of Sustainability)	Curious about recyclability and separability of CicloPak;	Not specifically mentioned.	Neutral

			stressed MRFs must be on board.		
13	NPP Ireland 	Eoin McDonagh (Director)	<p>Stressed that many companies would be happy to move away from fossil-based plastics, but the economics are currently a barrier.</p> <p>Strong interest in bio-films even with slight colour/opacity; bio-based films with similar performance of thin EVOH for oxygen barrier could be adopted.</p>	<p>Unsure about the technical recycling process, but trusts the rule that $\leq 5\%$ adhesives/coatings of the total packaging, is acceptable for recyclability.</p>	<p>Positive-openness to engaging further, including potentially facilitating trials or customer feedback, and willing to consider a letter of support for funding purposes.</p>
14	Origin Green (Bord Bia) 	Martin Hofler (Senior Sustainability Manager, Ambassador)	<p>High barrier properties and biodegradability promising.</p> <p>Infrastructure gaps in Ireland pose commercial challenges.</p> <p>Stressed packaging validation and material compatibility assessments with Teagasc PCF.</p> <p>Identified niche opportunities for meat intermediate packaging and milk cartons.</p>	<p>Circularity potential. Identified key niche application such as beverage labels, on-the-go packaging (coffee cups).</p>	<p>Neutral</p>

15	<p>Pilgrim's Europe</p>	<p>Neil Ryan (Customer Packaging Innovation Lead), and Matt Harris, (Head of Packaging Europe)</p>	<p>Microbial protein material may be most relevant for Pilgrim's in non-consumer-facing packaging formats, such as primals or business-to-business transfers, and suggested that applications in shrink barrier bags and other non-retail uses could be a strong early fit.</p>	<p>Not specifically mentioned.</p>	<p>Positive- Proposed follow-up to align tech with Pilgrim's strategy, explore funding/collaboration, and engage Athlone research facility.</p>
16	<p>REPAK</p>	<p>Tom Gaynor (Chief Operations Officer)</p>	<p>REPAK would support new materials with lower fees or promotion only if recyclability is proven. However, chemical recycling not yet recognised. Personally, interested in the low-cost PET depolymerisation process, seen as more promising than high-energy alternatives.</p>	<p>Not specifically mentioned.</p>	<p>Neutral</p>
17	<p>RH Packaging</p>	<p>Ivor Leenane (Sales Director UK & USA)</p>	<p>Niche market exists for bio-based/compostable materials, but cost is main barrier. EPR regulations and vested interests</p>	<p>Not specifically mentioned. Suggested de-risking claims, ensure recyclability and compostability</p>	<p>Neutral</p>

			complicate adoption; success requires targeted niches and regulatory alignment.	compliance of CicloPak/CicloSeal, and align with right partner/application for traction.	
18	<p>Sinclair International</p>	Scott Howarth (R&D Director)	Not specifically mentioned.	<p>Potential for compostable fruit label adhesives. Must aligns with evolving fruit label requirements: adhesives must meet food-contact regulations, peel cleanly without residue, and degrade in home/industrial composting. Encouraged further application-specific testing: loop tack, 90-degree peel, and shear assessments, with the added requirement that there be no cohesive failure. Benchmark against these specific industry-standard tests, such as TAPPI and ASTM protocols.</p>	Positive -offered to send documentation on the exact procedures Sinclair uses across its operations, offering to stay in touch and expressing interest in seeing further technical data for any potential collaboration or product integration.
19	<p>TIPA</p>	Nina (Vice President of R&D)	Suggested to prepare thin flexible films (20–40 µm); tests in commercially relevant	Strong interest in compostable adhesives, suitable for pressure-sensitive label	Positive - offer further follow-up and invited the team to reach out with

			<p>scales; encouraged reducing sample thickness below 100 μm to evaluate performance vs EVOH. As reference, TIPA films achieve OTR <1 even <20 μm thickness and are home-compostable. Explore coatings as another application route.</p>	<p>applications on fresh produce. In terms of testing and characterisation, several technical parameters that TIPA uses to evaluate materials: seal strength, oxygen and water vapour transmission rates (OTR and WVTR), coefficient of friction, transparency/opacity, impact resistance, and elongation.</p>	<p>more data or questions as the work progresses.</p>
20	<p>UKRI UK Research and Innovation</p>	<p>Gavin Lewis (Innovation Lead), Nick Cliffe (Deputy)</p>	<p>Interested in EVOH-level oxygen barrier potential of CicloPak films. They cautioned that even high-performance bio-based materials often fail to commercialise if they cannot be produced cost-effectively from inexpensive, abundant feedstocks. Possible opportunities in meat packaging (thick multilayer barrier films used in meat aging and transport), food-to-go</p>	<p>Interested in compostable adhesives for niche applications (fruit stickers); emphasised techno-economic assessment for CicloPak and CicloSeal.</p>	<p>Positive- offering to remain available for future follow-up.</p>

			packaging (coatings for paperboard), compostable caddy liners used for food waste collection, small-format flexible packaging (sachets for salad dressings or energy gels), absorbent pads used in meat trays and tobacco packaging in the Global South.		
21		Roy Cox & Thomas Baker (Technical Specialists)	Interested in CicoPak film barrier properties vs EVOH; recyclability implications raised; stressed need for biodegradability standards compliance: European norms EN 13432 (industrial composting) and EN 17427 (home composting).	Strong potential in compostable fruit stickers; need to validate 'plastic-free' claims under regulation.	Positive- Offered to support technical discussions and university-commercialisation pathways, shared contact info, and noted WRAP-Belfast/Queen's University collaborations, suggesting possible synergies with CicoPak's materials and applications.

Annex III – EcoPlastiC on the EC Innovation Radar

The Innovation Radar is a European Commission initiative to identify high potential innovations and innovators in EU-funded research and innovation projects. The goal is to allow every citizen, public official, professional and business person to discover the outputs of EU innovation funding and give them a chance to seek out innovators who could follow in the footsteps of successful companies, all of whom received EU funding in their early days. All innovations that are part of the Innovation radar are contributing to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Information about EU-funded innovations from high-quality projects is visible and accessible to the public via the [Innovation Radar platform](#). The innovations can also be explored by maturity levels: Exploring, Tech Ready, Business Ready and Market Ready.

Published:

TUS: [Recalcitrant plastics replacement using virgin-to- virgin loops](#) (Business Ready)

IMGGE: [Polyhydroxyalkanoate purification process using enzyme cocktail](#) (Exploring)

TUS: [Mechanical/green chemical waste PET depolymerisation](#) (Business Ready)

TUS, AVE, KTH: [Prototype production of eco-plastic trays and films from food waste based-SCP, PHA-rich biomass for packaging](#) (Business Ready)

AVE: [Precision fermentation for PHAs, the production of protein rich biomass and biogas](#) (Tech Ready)

Planned:

TUS: **PerPETual Virgin to Virgin Loops for PET Plastics** (TRL 6)

TUS: **CicloSeal Technology: A Novel Bio-Based Adhesive Platform** (TRL 4)

KTH: **CicloPACK Multilayer Films for Packaging Applications** (TRL 4)

IMGGE: **Eco-Friendly Coat Hangers and Tags from Agro-Waste and Biopolymers** (TRL 6)

NOVA, IMGGE: **Sustainable Recovery and Purification of Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs)** (TRL 4)